

Digital Literacies and Creativity of Language Learning in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to uncover and describe the digital literacy of higher education students and lecturers as well as the creativity of language learning which is emphasized in the use of digital media, which includes four aspects of language skills integrated in other learning. This research was conducted by the desk study and case study methods. The desk study method is carried out through a literature study on digital literacy at higher education based on related documents, such as activity reports, archives, and evidence of student performance. This case study is carried out through observation of learning activities and FGDs or in-depth interviews with the parties involved, such as students, lecturers, and institutional managers. Then, the data is analyzed qualitatively and the tendency is interpreted based on triangulation of data. The results of this study indicate that the digital literacy of higher education students and lecturers, especially in the class under study is realized through several fields of digital media utilization, such as for designing and displaying learning media through laptops and android mobiles, interaction / communication in learning by utilizing android mobiles through WhatsApp and Facebook channels, displaying assignments and student work via WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube and microblogging. All activities in various digital modes make use of language. The creativity of language learning integrated with other lessons is dominated by an emphasis on reading skills (40%), speaking (25%), writing (20%), and listening (15%).

KEYWORDS: Creative Learning, Digital Literacies, Language Learning, Higher Education

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1. INTRODUCTION

The development of information technology has touched every joint of human life. According to Kurnia and Astuti (2017), more and more technology users in Indonesia. This is evidenced by the data obtained against technology users, especially in using the internet or social networks that utilize technology. Based on data released by the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers (APJII, 2016) it is known that until now the number of internet users in Indonesia has reached 132.7 million people from 256.2 million people of Indonesia's population, which is equivalent to almost 51.8% of Indonesia's population.

The increase in internet users or digital technology does not necessarily guarantee an increase in wise behavior in the use of IT. The fact shows that the large number of internet users in Indonesia and the high frequency of accessing information content and social media, does not necessarily guarantee the maturity of Indonesian netizens' thinking in using the internet (Kurnia and Astuti, 2017). This is also proven by the rampant cases of misuse of information technology through social networks and the use of the internet for fraud, and even the widespread hoax among the public. If the community is not careful in using IT, it is certain that they will fall, even they can become victims of IT. Tamburaka (2013) states that with the development of technology in the field of information technology triggers major changes in digitalization technology, namely the condition of all printed and electronic media content can be combined and distributed (Awgichew & Seyoum, 2017), so that access to information through digital media will occur so quickly and in a broad reach (Edzan, 2008; Sutrisna, 2018). In this case, carefulness and wise attitude, and digital literacy are needed by the community.

The importance of digital literacy for the community is not only caused by the high exposure of the media in every inch of human life, but also due to several other factors. First, the important role of information in the democratic process results in a person being obliged to increase his ability to digital literacy. All information in the principle of democracy can be openly accessed by every community. Second, the important role of cultural participation and citizenship. To be able to play an optimal role in the realm of culture and citizenship, digital literacy support is really needed. Through digital literacy, everyone can access information and disseminate information related to cultural content and citizenship wisely. Third, the development of popular culture makes everyone

more and more access to something through digital media, which needs to be balanced with digital literacy capabilities (Koltay, 2011). Thus, the important role of digital literacy is also driven by the high growth of media that is not comparable with human ability to compensate.

In general, digital literacy refers to the ability to relate to hypertextual information in the sense of reading non-sequential and carrying out other activities aided by computers or digital media (Hundley & Holbrook, 2013). The concept of digital literacy does not stand alone, but is related to several other concepts of literacy, including literacy and language skills (Mary Olufunke, 2013). In this case digital literacy can be integrated or used to support learning creativity (Bauer & Kenton, 2005; Cervetti, Damico & Pearson, 2006; Lei, 2009; Bal, 2018), one of which is creativity in language learning. That is, digital literacy that is owned by instructors and students can support each other in creating creative learning activities. Digital media platforms that can be used in learning activities vary depending on the characteristics and abilities of each user, including the carrying capacity to access them (Manca & Ranieri, 2013; Bal, 2018; Durriyah, & Zuhdi, 2018; Kassem, 2018). It needs to be used as a basis for consideration because the advantages and disadvantages are always inherent in digital media and it is the responsibility of educators to optimize all the advantages that exist by pressing all the weaknesses of the digital media (Ketut Sudarsana, Pusparani, Selasih, Juliantari, & Wayan Renawati, 2019). The excellence of digital media is that it is an effective tool to support learning activities (Bauer & Kenton, 2005, Cervetti, Damico & Pearson, 2006).

According to Brown & Mayisela (2015), South Africa is recorded as a country that is quite progressive in including digital literacy as part of the formal education curriculum. Starting from the tertiary level (2012), digital literacy is subsequently adopted as part of the basic curriculum. The study of digital literacy in students themselves in general has begun in 2010, then continues on more specific topics such as the use of blogging, visual arts through digital media, to digital story-telling and music making. When the digital literacy curriculum was adopted in 2014, South Africa had a fairly mature preparation.

Meanwhile, in learning activities at the STKIP Agama Hindu Amlapura (hereinafter referred to as STKIP-AH) the development of varied digital literacy in learning and at the same time to support the creativity of students has recently been carried out and intensified since the Covid-19 pandemic hit Indonesia with the enactment of learning from home. Digital literacy is optimized in language learning activities that are integrated in other learning. The emphasized aspect refers to the skills of listening, reading, speaking and writing.

Creativity in language learning, as an important psychological trait, has not been sufficiently touched by researchers (Pishghadam, Khodadady, & Zabihi, 2011). Palaniappan (2007) investigated the relationship between creativity and academic achievement among 497 students from three secondary schools in Malaysia. The results of the study revealed that creativity is positively related to academic achievement. However, the prediction of the power of creativity in supporting academic success has not yet been replicated in different contexts, between different participants, and through different instruments. This provides a loophole for further studies, even in different packages. From a psychological point of view, creativity is an important factor because it provides a framework for an individual's creativity and also specific differences between individuals. According to Meera & Remya (2010), if you want to develop creativity, the classroom environment must contain a variety of materials and encourage many different experiences. Meanwhile, this research focuses on creativity in learning Indonesian that is integrated in other lessons through digital literacy support.

Similar research was carried out by Bal (2018) about the experience of reading and writing students in the digital age through Wattpad. The results of this study indicate that some students are more interest and happy to develop ideas and express themselves in digital media compared to conventional learning. Durriyah and Zuhdi (2018) have also examined digital literacy, but in relation to learning English as a second language. In the research revealed that various popular digital media used by teachers and students as a medium for teaching literacy are facebook, blogs, skype, and whatsapp. Both of these studies are similar to this study, both of which examine digital literacy, but in this study more emphasis is placed on creativity in Indonesian language learning integrated in other learning.

Based on the description above, this study seeks to uncover and describe two things. First, the digital literacy of STKIP-AH students and lecturers reflected through digital media in supporting learning activities. Second, learning creativity that is integrated with other lessons, through digital media, which supports four skills, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted by the Desk Study and Case Study methods. The Desk Study method is carried out through a literature study on digital literacy at higher education STKIP Agama Hindu Amlapura, Bali (STKIP-AH) based on related documents, such as activity reports, archives, and evidence of student performance. The aim is to explore the digital literacy of STKIP-AH students and lecturers reflected through the use of digital media in supporting learning activities. While Case Study explores the creativity of language learning which is emphasized through the use of digital media. This case study is carried out through observation of learning activities and FGDs or in-depth interviews with the parties involved, such as students, lecturers, and institutional managers. Subjects studied were 20 Hindu Religious Education Study Program students (one class) and 8 lecturers teaching in the class, and 4 institutional managers. All related data collection processes are supported by the use of documentation and interview guidelines,

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which contain several key elements such as the use of digital media, the focus of language skills emphasized, and the creativity of learning undertaken. Data were analyzed qualitatively by combining data collected through triangulation of data, which was then presented narratively and supported by a presentation of the percentage table of intensity of the use of digital media in the development of students' language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that the digital literacy of STKIP-AH students and lecturers, especially in the class under study is realized through several fields of digital media utilization, such as to design and display learning media through laptops and android mobile phones; interaction / communication in learning by utilizing an android mobile via WhatsApp and facebook channels; as well as displaying assignments and student work through WhatsApp, facebook, youtube and microblogging. The use of digital media in learning as a form of digital literacy that is owned by lecturers and students can be seen in the following table.

TABLE 1: The Form of Digital Literacy in Learning Activities

No	Field of Digital Media Utilization	Specific Form of Digital Literacy
1	Design / create learning media or presentations	Make power points with various models / designs and displays by utilizing office power point microsof. Make quizzes by using Google Form as the medium
2	Showing learning media or presenting learning material	Display power point slides with a variety of views, as shown at once every one slide or gradually displayed each slide presentation. The way text is displayed varies through animation and sound choices. Sending google form links via Whatsapp group so that material is also indirectly presented via Whatsapp digital mode.
3	Establish interaction/ communication in learning	Utilization of various digital channels, such as Whatsapp and Facebook Used a variety of applications available on Whatsapp and Facebook to facilitate interaction.
4	Create / display student assignments	Used Whatsapp for sending tasks, either directly written to the Whatsapp body or sent files in the form of word, pdf, or recording / video in accordance with the assignment Used of Facebook in creating and sending assignments for written assignments / appearance categories The use of Youtube to create and display student assignments, either through the lecturer Youtube account, the institution Youtube account, or the student Youtube account for types of performance assignments, such as presentations, counseling, or performances The use of lecturer microblogging or the website of the institution to display student assignments in the form of writing, such as writing papers, essays, reports, and literary works.

All activities according to TABLE 1 that utilize various digital modes are also integrated in it regarding the use of Indonesian. The creativity of language learning integrated with other subjects is dominated by an emphasis on reading skills (40%), speaking (25%), writing (20%), and listening (15%). These results can be seen in detail in the following table.

TABLE 2: Utilization of Digital Media and Language Learning Creativity

No	Language Skills	Digital media	Digital mode / platform utilized	Learning activity	Percentage of Intensity of language skills emphasis
1	Listening skills	Android mobile, laptop	Whatsapp, Facebook, Youtube	Students listen to information from various digital media (Whatsapp, Facebook, YouTube) in the form of audio or audiovisual, then tell the content that is listened to	15%
2	Reading skills	Android mobile, laptop	Whatsapp, Facebook, Blog	Students read information / news from digital media (Whatsapp, Facebook, blogs), then rewrites the content that is read or distributed	40%
3	Speaking skills	Android mobile, laptop	Whatsapp (voice recorder), facebook (live broadcast of speaking practice or	Students perform various practices of communicating or talking through digital media (Whatsapp, Facebook, YouTube	25%

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			video upload speaking), youtube (video upload of speaking practice)		
4	Writing skills	Android mobile, laptop	Whatsapp, Facebook (write ideas on Whatsapp / Facebook bodies)	Students write ideas with a variety of text genres on Whatsapp and Facebook, then get comments from others.	20%

Based on this table it can be seen that in each emphasis aspects of language skills that are integrated with other lessons WhatsApp and Facebook digital modes are always used. This implies that students and lecturers have adequate literacy in utilizing the two digital modes. Creativity that occurs in digital mode as presented in the table, including posting ideas on WhatsApp or Facebook homepage. Furthermore, the posts containing the learning content received responses or comments from other students or the general public, so the language learning process took place openly through the digital mode. Students also upload videos on WhatsApp or Facebook. In this case, students also learn to speak and communicate something, even though the content is substantially related to other subject matter. This is what is meant by the creativity of language learning that is integrated in other lessons. Meanwhile, YouTube and blogs (microblogging) are only used in a limited way because the digital literacy of students and lecturers about the use of the two digital modes is also limited.

The variations in the use of various digital modes are adjusted to the carrying capacity and digital literacy abilities of lecturers and STKIP-AH students. This is also supported by the recognition of Manca & Ranieri (2013), Bal (2018), Durriyah & Zuhdi (2018), Kassem (2018) who advocate and support each user, including supporting support to support him to assist in the use of various modes digital for smooth interaction and learning optimization. Ketut Sudarsana, Pusparani, Selasih, Juliantari, & Wayan Renawati, (2019) and expert assignments are needed to develop this learning application (Richards, 2013). If the advantages of digital media are optimized, of course they will achieve efficiency and compatibility of learning (Bauer & Kenton, 2005, Cervetti, Damico & Pearson, 2006), but if they are not suitable in the selection to support digital literacy, lecturers and students cannot compare, change modes digital utilization can hamper the learning process. Therefore, various digital modes that support learning in STKIP-AH, such as WhatsApp, facebook, youtube, and microblogging are used because lecturers and students have literacy about the digital mode. Related, in general, lecturers and students are able to use WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, and digital microblogging modes that are selected to support learning creativity.

The dominant aspect of language skills emphasized in integrated language learning activities is reading skills. So, the stimulation given by the lecturer in emphasizing the creativity of students' language through digital mode is through giving various reading materials to students. The reading material is distributed through digital mode so that it appears that digital literacy and creativity support one another. Izazi & Tengku-Sepora (2020) revealed that communication mediated by digital media has significantly driven changes in the nature of language, sometimes even obscuring written and spoken languages. This will certainly be valuable learning for students in learning languages in accordance with the reality faced due to the use of technology or digital media.

Richards (2013) suggests that teachers can plan for the use of different tasks in different levels of creativity to emphasize linguistic aspects that are integrated in other learning. For example, learning is packaged through the activities of asking, practicing, discussing, and playing roles, so that through various activities students get practical language experience. Whatever the lesson, it takes some stimulus to stimulate creativity in learning through creative media (Fisher, 2005), which can be combined with digital media. Therefore, according to Palaniappan (2007), to achieve creativity in language learning that is integrated with other subjects, freedom in expressing oneself by students must be optimized. This self-expression tends to be realized through speaking and writing skills.

However, in this finding it turns out that the proportion of reading skills given more emphasis, which reached 40%. This happens because the lecturer has the perception of other abilities will grow if students have extensive knowledge related to various things. This vast knowledge can be obtained through reading activities. Furthermore, from the adequate reading skills and extensive knowledge, then students are directed to express themselves in speaking and writing, so that the emphasis on aspects of speaking skills reaches 25% and writing skills 20%.

Richards (2013) mentions that creative people are slightly different from others who are not creative. Creative people can use different types of knowledge and abilities compared to people who are less creative. They are able to utilize different thought processes. Creativity depends on being able to analyze and evaluate situations and identify new ways to respond to them, including in this regard the choice and use of various digital modes and combining them to become multimodal. Burton (2010) explains creative teaching means assessing activities and materials to support creative teaching, the provision of creative tasks, and creative discussion through the use of varied digital media. Thus, creative language learning will also be included in it.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion, it can be concluded that the digital literacy of STKIP-AH students and lecturers, especially in the class under study is realized through several fields of digital media utilization, such as for designing and displaying learning media through laptops and android mobile phones, interaction / communication in learning by utilizing cellphones android via WhatsApp and facebook channels, displaying assignments and student work through WhatsApp, facebook, youtube and microbloging. That means students and lecturers of STKIP-AH have literacy skills in using WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube and microbloging. The creativity of language learning integrated with other lessons is dominated by an emphasis on reading skills (40%), speaking (25%), writing (20%), and listening (15%). So, the dominant language skills emphasized in the integrated language learning activities are reading skills. Reading skills are seen as opening the way or as a key to opening other skills, so this is given a dominant proportion.

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